

Circular Approach for Eco-Composite Bulky Product

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Executive Summary

Looking at the circular economy boost, and with the aim of enhancing recycling activities in three industrial sectors, this report tries to study the reverse logistics chain.

In particular, the three sectors involved (automotive, furniture and building) have low levels of reuse, except for the first, mainly linked to old vehicles repair.

After studying the reverse logistics chain, it is assumed its greater complexity in comparison with the forward logistics, mainly because its higher level of uncertainty. This usually implies higher costs. On the contrary, products obtained are low-value. Thus, consequently, most of the companies in these sectors do not develop recycling and reusing activities.

In order to change this scenario, the first task is to develop a deep analysis of the different activities involved in the reverse logistics, which will allow identifying the key performance indicators (KPIs) in each case.

As a result, the most critical activities are linked to collection, inspection and sorting, and product recovery. In each case, a list of KPIs has been identified, considering the stakeholder's point of view.

Specifically, some of them are related to costs, process complexity, traceability, final product value (linked to quality), regulation and legislations and user behaviour, the latter being understood as the need of change to a more sustainable and efficient consumption pattern.

From these results, a new reverse logistics model can be developed by addressing all the critical activities involved (transport means, monitoring activities, identification and sorting, etc.) This is the task to be completed in the following months, with the challenge of defining an optimal reverse logistics chain for each sector.

Furthermore, in order to define circular business models and design the different phases involved, several best practices and technologies have been identified as references, some of them focused on the reverse logistics processes management and traceability.

Finally, with the aim of With the objective of being able to make comparisons between the possible options (in each of the steps) that arise throughout the logistics chain, the use of a Multi-Criteria Decision

Tool based on the CRITIC (CRiteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation) multicriteria assessment model is proposed, taking into account economic, technical, environmental, social and legal aspects.

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1. Introduction

1.1. Description of the document and pursue

The objective of this work is to analyse and optimise the reverse logistics chain, by first identifying the different activities involved in this process. Thus, it will allow to identify the critical tasks and key performance indicators to be considered in order to define the optimal reverse logistics chain.

To this end, the first part of this report addresses the definition and identification of the reverse logistics chain and its comparison to the forward logistics. Specifically, the three industrial sectors involved in the project (automotive, furniture and building) are studied in order to identify their specific reverse logistics activities.

Afterwards, the Supply Chain Operations Reference-model (SCOR) model is described, since it will be the pattern to follow for the operational analysis of the different reverse logistics for each sector to address in the task 5.1 of the project.

Finally, the main key performance indicators (KPIs) of the reverse logistic chain are identified, taking into account the main activities involve in this process, and specifically for each of the industrial sectors addressed.

1.2. WPs and Tasks related with the deliverable

This deliverable is included in WP5, and more specifically, within the task 5.1, of which the main objective is to optimise the reverse logistics chain of the three sectors analysed (automotive, furniture and building), specifically the collection activity, to deploy the most appropriate tools for smooth and streamlined transportation and logistics processes.

This way, one of its main aims is to analyse the reverse logistics for each industrial sector and identify the critical activities involved considering aspects such associated costs, ease of the processes, obtaining of valuable products that allow recovering the investment made, health and safety requirements and environmental issues. Afterwards, and related to these activities, the most important KPIs (Key Performance Indicators) have been identified in order to optimise the entire reverse logistics chain efficiency.

The next challenge is the identification of strategies and technologies for transport and logistics optimisation (adequate means of transport, route planning, traceability and monitoring, demand planning and forecasting, location of collection points, warehouse positioning and management, safeguard product quality and safety and other). This activity has been being developed in parallel with the WP6, and more specifically with activities 6.1 and 6.2, and is included in the updated version of this report in M36.

2. Characterization of reverse logistics chain of materials and products

As mentioned in Section 1, this WP aims to characterise each phase involved in the supply chain and inverse logistics related to the three sectors addressed in the project: automotive, furniture and constructions. Thus, this task implies the identification of the main activities in each case.

In general, logistics indicates how the products are transported from producer to customer, while reverse logistics works in an opposite way (Autry, 2005). Specifically, reverse logistics may be defined as a process of moving goods from their place of use, back to their place of manufacture for reprocessing, re-filling, repairs or recycling / waste disposal. It was presented at first in 1992 by Stock (Autry, 2005). With the increasing people's awareness in environmental protection and progressive regulatory constraints in some countries (e.g. Japan or European Union countries), the economic value of reverse logistics is gradually increasing.

In this project context, the main objective of reverse logistics is to foster and boost recycling and reuse (material reuse and remanufacturing / refurbishing) and reduce the hazardous materials disposal.

More specifically, reverse logistics process involves the following activities:

- Handling of return merchandise (collection and transportation)
- Increasing recycling and reuse rates
- Decreasing hazardous materials disposal

When compared the reverse logistics process to forward logistics, the main differences identified are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparison between forward and reverse logistics processes.

As mentioned previously, reverse logistics substantially differ from forward logistics. In fact, first one is more complex and harder to predict, mainly because customers are the ones who initiate the process.

One of the main differences refers to collection and transportation since products are moved from several origins to the main destination (in case of assuming the centralised point to collect products before their sorting and treatment processes). This situation involves not clear routes, which means more time needed to decide on destination of recycled products.

Furthermore, packaging is also different in reverse logistics since recycled products are usually not packaged or improperly packaged, which results in damages to them. In addition, this involves that they can be stacked.

In general, logistics costs in reverse logistics are higher due to several reasons:

- Lower vehicle utilisation, linked to lower volume of products;
- Lower utilisation rates, because of low level of standardization; and,
- Longer time in inspecting, sorting and process the different types of products.

Likewise, and after analysing both processes, other serious barriers link to the reverse chain are:

- Legal issues:
 - This is a very cumbersome and time-consuming process and non-compliance may mean that the manufacturer will have to face legal action.
 - Many organizations consider reverse goods as waste and they do not want to spend their resources on processing waste.
- The goods are considered unworthy of any investment.

Furthermore, waste treatment is another priority measurement for nowadays environmental protection and maintains the sustainability for future, which refers to the methods that have to be done to guarantee that the waste has the least negative impact and hazardous influences to the environment. Waste treatment has also been divided into many specific forms in different areas in worldwide due to the law. The main way of controlling of the environmental pollution and waste which are harmful to human health is to impose on waste resources harmless reduction treatment processes. In this sense, the recycling of industrial waste must be developed according to the specific characteristics of a given industry production, as well as pay attention to the technical feasibility, the competitive product and economic benefits among other factors.

In this context, the concept of circular economy arises as “resource-product-litter-renewable resources” process, be based on three main activities: reduce, reuse and recycle.

Then, this section aims to study and analyse the current status and development of reverse logistics in the three sectors: automotive, furniture and construction. In other words, its scope is to answer the following questions:

- What is the importance of reverse logistics?
- What are the exiting problems in reverse logistics?

2.1. Automotive sector

Currently, forward logistics of automobile industry have been developed in a good stage and this is the key area of focus for third-party logistics companies now. However, because of the mature of automotive consumer market competition, innovation and the rise of global environmental awareness, reverse logistics in the automotive sector may assume greater significance.

The concept of recycling has arisen since more and more people have been realised the importance of sustainability. Not only because recycling can provide the decreasing of waste but can also effectively revalue this waste, which implies a better use of resources and more sustainable processes.

From 2015 the industry must ensure that 95% (up from 85% previously) of the vehicle by weight is re-used, recycled or recovered. The sector has been achieving the previous target, but the new tougher limits have required considerable investment from both the vehicle manufacturers (VMs) and the recycling industry in new processes.

With the arrival of innovative new materials and powertrains, including lithium-ion batteries, the sector is developing processes to ensure the effective re-use, recycling and recovery of future vehicles and their components. Industry is also developing alternative uses – second life opportunities – for new battery types, including for energy storage for projects outside the auto sector, e.g. storing electricity from solar panels in the home.

When a vehicle reaches the end of its life it must be disposed of in an environmentally responsible way through an Authorised Treatment Facility (ATF). Through the End of Life Vehicles (ELVs) Directive, vehicle manufactures have an obligation to provide free take-back for cars and light commercial vehicles. The vehicle can then be disposed of and parts re-used, recycled, or used for energy recovery.

As mentioned, to recycle a vehicle, it must be taken to an authorised centre (ATF), where each material will be treated properly without the recycling itself producing any pollutants. The first stage is to decontaminate the vehicle, in which batteries, liquids, plastics, textiles and wiring are removed. After that, an assessment is made of what can be recycled from what remains of the vehicle. When only metal remains, it is compressed reducing its volume to be stored or taken to finish recycling. The remains of the vehicle are pressed to be moved to the shredding plant. A hammer mill crushes them into fragments of

between 20 and 40 centimetres. The fragments pass through magnetic currents that separate the metal parts (approximately 75%) from the rest of the material. The scrap is sent to the steel industry, where it is recycled

Related to the recycling process of materials from the end-of-life vehicles, Cui & Roven (2010) defined a model which shows the typical structure for this activity:

Figure 2: Automotive sector reverse logistics process. Cui and Roven (2010)

Based on this scheme, the disassembly of automotive vehicles usually is a selective process, in which selecting out the hazardous or usable parts is a necessary step in automotive recycling. More specifically, this methodology allows to take a part a series of components or the sub-components of a product; or to break down a product in small little parts based on the provided goal.

The mentioned methodology involved different steps, following the data and information provided by Grupo Bellver partner:

- Step 1: Analysis of input and output product, to figure out the reusable, valuable and hazardous parts and resources of the product. In the automotive sector there are many statistics on which cars are scrapped and when. The average life of a vehicle before it reaches a scrapyard is usually known (e.g. 13 years in

Spain). Therefore, the number of vehicles and their composition (materials) can be predicted by looking at the sales statistics. The accuracy level is 80% and the remaining 20% is because some are deregistered before and others. With such a long lead time, it allows how how to the composition (metal/plastic) of the vehicle evolves and to adapt (in machinery)

- Step 2: Analysis of assembly, to identify participate components, elements level and former assembly queue.
- Step 3: Analysis of uncertainties and risks, related to defective components and joint parts. The prices of resale (second-hand) parts can vary greatly depending on use, age, and whether it has been involved in an accident. Metal prices are set by the London Stock Exchange and are global worldwide. Recycled plastics prices are global and are inversely conditioned by the price of crude oil. In other words, if the price of crude oil rises, the price of virgin plastic rises, so it is easier to sell recycled plastic, and vice versa
- Step 4: Establishment of the disassembly strategy (non-destructive way or a destructive way).

2.2. Furniture sector

The European furniture industry faces a variety of economic and regulatory challenges – including manufacturing growth in emerging markets, improved logistics (reducing export costs from India, China etc.), declined tariffs on foreign trade, increased demand for low-cost items within the EU, increased costs of raw material, labour and energy within the EU and increasing consumer demand for sustainable products¹.

More specifically, addressing the concept of circular economy into the furniture industry could help this sector to reduce the waste and environmental impact by recapturing the remaining value of products at the end of lifecycle.

Traditionally, this sector has been linear focused and is lacking the transition towards a circular economy. One of the main reasons might be that furniture is generally spoken big and heavy, thus hard to handle and represents a relatively low residual value, therefore, it makes the industry hard to transform towards the Circular Economy model.

¹ European Remanufacturing Network Market Study (2015)

Additionally, there are not many previous experiences that encourage companies to shift towards Circular Economy.

Currently, this industry generates huge amounts of waste which is mainly sent to landfills. In fact, many furniture products are disposed although they are not at the end of their lifecycle and the conditions of materials are appropriate to be reused again.

According to European Federation of Furniture Manufacturers (UEA) statistics, in the EU furniture waste accounts for more than 4 % of the total municipal solid waste, of which 80-90 % is incinerated or dumped in landfills, with 10 % recycled. Where reuse does occur, it is mostly through commercial second-hand shops, social enterprise companies or charities.

For that reason, this industry is one of the sectors which have future potential by developing a circular economy business model, by creating new revenue streams by reusing and refurbishing furniture products. However, it largely depends on the financial feasibility of the process (it seems to be the first step to change the current pattern). In this context, an efficient management of reverse logistics is fundamental to enable furniture companies to shift towards Circular Economy. This should enable them to develop a viable supply chain of collection, repairing, refurbishing, remanufacturing and reselling. More specifically, there are major concerns with regards on handling logistics and transportation.

Pokharel and Mutha (2009) developed an overview on reverse logistics that can be summarised in the following framework:

Figure 3: Furniture reverse logistics process. Pokharel and Mutha (2009).

In general, in the reverse logistics processes different categories are identified: general, inspection and consolidation, integrating manufacturing and remanufacturing and product modularity. More specifically, the process above also includes more activities: disassembly, remanufacturing, supply chain planning, coordinating, inventory control and, in many cases, after-sales services. In the final sections, reverse logistics outputs diversify between product pricing and competition and customer relation.

In order to foster and boost this model, several identified barriers to circular furniture have to be broken down:

- Lower quality materials and poor design: the current move away from solid wood and metal furniture to cheaper materials, restricts the potential for a successful second life;
- REACH Regulation (on Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals): the lack of information on chemicals contained in products and on ways how to deal with them appropriately joins to the overrun of hazardous substances treatment;
- Poor consumer information and availability of spares: consumers are rarely given guidance on how to maintain and repair furniture, and the lack of availability of spare parts encourages the purchase of new furniture;
- Limited collection and reverse logistics infrastructure: currently there are weak drivers and underinvestment in the collection and logistics for furniture take-back
- High cost of repair and refurbishment: transport and labour costs are high, making any significant repair and refurbishment costly
- Weak demand for second-hand furniture: the price differential between new furniture against the cost of second-life furniture, is not significant enough to drive more sustainable purchasing behaviour;
- Poor offer for recycled materials: end markets for recycled materials, post deconstruction, are underdeveloped. Some second-hand channels are Ebay and Freecycle, however, the number of items traded in this way is difficult to quantify
- Weak over-arching policy drivers: typically, furniture is not managed in accordance with the waste hierarchy, with reuse failing to be prioritised over recycling, incineration and landfill.

2.3. Construction sector

The application of circular economy to the building sector is less than straight forward. In fact, existing frameworks frequently express principles, but it is needed to both the appropriate ecosystem and the individual components to change. In this case, issues such as governance, regulation and business models could potentially be more important than design and engineering.

Effectively, the regulatory framework is one of the aspects that most affects in this context, identifying different administrative obstacles that cause not to promote the circular economy but quite the opposite. First, a significant percentage of the waste generated is illegal dumping derived from small works, renovations, etc. that are not properly managed and that the lack of control does not allow the application of the appropriate sanctions. In addition, official production statistics are not available, which makes traceability difficult, and does not favor selective collection, which is critical to improving the quality of the recycled material. Furthermore, the main problem is associated to the difficulties derived from the legislation when carrying out the reuse of land and waste between different works. This regulation often introduces many administrative requirements that complicate and delay such reuse.

Moreover, cooperation between companies or entities of the same or different value chain, through which they develop exchanges (materials, waste, by-products, energy, water, information, etc.) is a great opportunity.

In parallel, the change of ownership model by the use or service model is, in many sectors, one of the most successful strategies to promote the circular economy ("*servitisation*"). There are therefore possibilities and opportunities to explore within the construction sector, the application of this type of business models in different construction products and facilities.

Related to the value chain, consumption and use of natural resources have generally followed a linear approach. Materials are sourced, used and finally disposed of as waste. Known as the take-make-use dispose model, this produces negative externalities that include rising carbon emissions, increased pressures on landfill, unsustainable levels of water extraction and widespread ecosystem pollution.

The built environment comprises the man-made elements of our surroundings such as buildings as well as infrastructure including

transportation, telecommunications, energy, water and waste systems. Design, planning, and construction contribute to the quality of the built environment, which has a significant impact on human health, well-being and productivity.

Currently, this sector is the world's largest consumer of raw materials. It accounts for 50% of global steel production and consumes more than 3 billion tonnes of raw materials².

In this context, a circular approach could help the sector to reduce its environmental footprint, and to avoid rising costs, delays, and other consequences of volatile commodity markets. Considering the technical cycle, man-made products are designed so that at the end of their service life – when they can no longer be repaired and reused for their original purpose their components are extracted and reused or remanufactured into new products. This avoids sending waste to landfill and creates a closed-loop cycle-.

In order to prolong product life, it is fundamental to design for long-term durability, utilisation and value of assets. Durable materials and robust construction standards can reduce maintenance costs and extend the economic viability of a building or structure. Standardised components manufactured off-site to higher quality control standards can minimise the risk of structural faults and reduce long-term maintenance requirements.

With this aim, a closed-loop supply chain is defined in which the life of the materials would extend beyond the lifespan of the buildings, and they could be used again in other buildings or secondary markets.

In this regard, a series of networks are established to prolong the life of materials:

- Recycling networks: simple structure network that is characterised by requiring a high number of products recovered, but of little unit value. Products go from the consumption phase to the raw materials phase.
- Remanufacturing networks: networks used to recover parts or components of products with a high value added. The products go from the consumption phase to the manufacture phase.
- Reuse networks: simultaneous circulation networks of original and reused products, in which the cost of transportation is the most significant. Products go from the consumption phase to the distribution phase.

² https://www3.weforum.org/docs/WEF_Shaping_the_Future_of_Construction_report_020516.pdf

The next figure shows the reverse logistics flow scheme in the building sector:

Figure 4: Reverse and forward logistics chain in the building sector. Del Río, M., Villoria Sáez, P., Torrijos Antelo, F. (2017).

In short, recovering and recycling valuable materials reduces resource use and minimises waste, and it can cut costs and earn revenues for stakeholders in the built environment.

Buildings and structures can be designed to allow component parts to be easily separated and recycled. Standardisation of components will also facilitate this process and increase recyclability. Designing for reuse has the potential to significantly reduce carbon emissions and mitigate fluctuating materials prices.

In this regard, the European Union, through the new Waste Directives, as well as the Management Protocol for construction and demolition waste in the EU, is promoting the concept of Circular Economy in order to achieve more ambitious waste recycling objectives, such as "recycling 70% of construction and demolition waste in 2020, thus closing the life cycle of products by increasing recycling and reuse

As a result of the analysis carried out so far of the reverse logistics chain, and its effects on the circular economy, several critical factors should be taken into account for its development effectively, and therefore, its successful implementation: associated costs, ease of the processes, obtaining of valuable products that allow recovering the

investment made, health and safety requirements and environmental issues. Objectively, three activities have a special effect in the factors mentioned: **collection, inspection and sorting and product recovery processes**. Therefore, the efficiency, effectiveness and economic viability of the entire reverse logistics are largely dependent on different methods to carry out them. For this reason, the key indicators to be identified in the next section will refer to those ones that have a maximum incidence in the optimisation of these activities.

3. Definition of KPIs in reverse logistics

After analysing the reverse logistics chain, the next step is to identify the most critical activities involved and their key performance indicators (KPIs) that have critical influence in the process success and its efficiency levels.

The development of the new reverse logistics flow will be based on the SCOR (Supply Chain Operations Reference) model. This will ease the diagnosis of the current flow, characterizing its processes and providing references for the formulation of metrics and best practices to achieve the best-in-class performance. This activity will be addressed in the second report within the task 5.1.

Specifically, The SCOR Green model proposes ways to monitor the environmental impact, based on the measure of factors such as carbon footprint, emissions and recycling

For that reason, this section aims to describe this model and its development process.

3.1. SCOR model definition

The Supply Chain Operations Reference-model (SCOR) has been developed and endorsed by the Supply-Chain Council (SCC), an independent not-for-profit corporation, as the cross-industry standard for supply-chain management. Its main objective is to establish a Process Reference Model.

In fact, the SCOR-model is a Reference Model; it does not have a mathematical description or heuristic methods, instead, it standardises the terminology and processes of a Supply Chain to model and, using specific parameters, compares and analyses different alternatives and strategies of the entire supply chain.

The SCOR model allows describing the business activities necessary to satisfy the demand of a client. The Model is organized around the five main management processes: Plan, Source, Make, Deliver and Return.

Figure 5: SCOR five Primary Management Process.

As shown in the graph, the Supply Chain contemplated within the Model includes from the suppliers of our suppliers, to the customers of our customers, that is, it considers the Supply Chain understood in a broad sense. The following describes the basic processes in general lines. The following table defines each of these five processes.

SCOR Process	Description
Plan	It analyses how to balance resources with requirements and how to establish and publicise the plans for the entire chain. In addition, it also addresses the general operation of the company and how to align the chain strategic plan with the financial plan
Source	It analyses how to carry out the scheduling of deliveries, the identification, selection and valuation of suppliers or the inventories management
Make	It involves the activities related to: production programming, product characteristics, testing stage and product preparation for its passage to the next stage of the logistics chain
Delivery	In this area all management processes related to customer

	requests and shipments are analysed, including warehouse management, product reception and verification by the client and its installation if necessary. Finally, it also involves the customer's invoicing
Return	This phase involves all the processes related to the return of the product and post-delivery service

Table 1: SCOR processes description.

Moreover, SCOR contains three levels of process detail (see Figure 6): Higher Level (types of processes), Level of Configuration (categories of processes) and Level of Processes Elements (decomposition of processes). In all these three levels, SCOR provides KPIs, and systematically divided into five Performance Attributes: reliability, flexibility, responsiveness, cost and assets.

In a fourth level (level of implementation), the elements are decomposed of processes in tasks. At level 4, companies incorporate improvements in their processes and systems, not being part of the SCOR model. This level is usually started with one or several pilot projects, then evaluate them and then extend them to the entire Supply Chain, adapting their organisation, technology, processes and people to achieve competitive advantage.

A process reference model contains:

- A standard description of process management
- A framework of relationships between standard processes
- Standard metrics to measure the performance of the processes
- Management of best practices of its kind
- Standard alignment for features and functionalities

The different levels of SCOR are presented and characterised by: the elements and processes that are identified in each one of them; the content of each one of the levels as well as the areas that they cover; and, their decomposition and interrelation upstream and downstream.

		Level			
		#	Description	Schematic	Comments
Supply-Chain Operations Reference-model 		1	Top Level (Process Types)		Level 1 defines the scope and content for the Supply Chain Operations Reference-model. Here basis of competition performance targets are set.
	2	Configuration Level (Process Categories)		A company's supply chain can be "configured-to-order" at Level 2 from 30 core "process categories." Companies implement their operations strategy through the configuration they choose for their supply chain.	
	3	Process Element Level (Decompose Processes)		Level 3 defines a company's ability to compete successfully in its chosen markets, and consists of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Process element definitions • Process element information inputs, and outputs • Process performance metrics • Best practices, where applicable • System capabilities required to support best practices • Systems/tools Companies "fine tune" their Operations Strategy at Level 3.	
	4	Implementation Level (Decompose Process Elements)		Companies implement specific supply-chain management practices at this level. Level 4 defines practices to achieve competitive advantage and to adapt to changing business conditions.	

Figure 6: SCOR Three Levels of Process Detail.

Level 1: At this level the scope and content of the SCOR model is defined by analysing the bases of competition and establishing the objectives of competitive performance, related to provisioning, production and supply.

Level 1 performance metrics are high-level measures that run through multiple SCOR processes. Some of the most commonly used first level key indicators are those represented in the following figure.

Performance Attribute	Customer-Facing			Internal-Facing	
	Reliability	Responsiveness	Flexibility	Cost	Assets
Delivery performance	✓				
Fill Rate	✓				
Perfect order fulfillment	✓				
Order fulfillment lead time		✓			
Supply-chain response time			✓		
Production flexibility			✓		
Supply chain management cost				✓	
Cost of goods sold				✓	
Value-added productivity				✓	
Warranty cost or returns processing cost				✓	
Cash-to-cash cycle time					✓
Inventory days of supply					✓
Asset turns					✓

Table 2: Level 1 Performance Metrics.

Subsequently, the values of the first level indicators are compared in a table with other companies' ones in its sector and other sectors, and qualify as Equals, with Advantage or Superiors. In this way, it is possible to analyse in which aspects the Supply Chain is disadvantaged, identify the necessary improvements, prioritise the necessary improvement projects and plan their execution at a global level.

Level 2: at this level, each SCOR level can be further described by process type.

SCOR Process Type	Characteristics
Planning	<p>A process that aligns expected resources to meet expected demand requirements.</p> <p>Planning processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Balance aggregated demand and supply ○ Consider consistent planning horizon ○ (Generally) occur at regular, periodic intervals ○ Can contribute to supply-chain response time

Execution	<p>A process triggered by planned or actual demand that changes the state of material goods. Execution processes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Generally, involve <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Scheduling/sequencing ▪ Transforming product, and/or ▪ Moving product to the next process ○ Can contribute to the order fulfillment cycle time
Enable	<p>A process that prepares, maintains, or manages information or relationships on which planning and execution processes rely</p>

Table 3: SCOR processes type characterisation.

In the second level 26 processes categories are considered, which are the Main categories that allow to configure the chain of practically any company: 5 to Plan, 3 to Procurement, 3 to Manufacturing, 4 to Distribution, 6 to Devolution (3 of Procurement and 3 of Distribution), and 5 to Enable. The first five are related to the planning type, the 16 intermediate ones to the executing type and the last 5 to the support type (enabling). The Enabling ones support planning and executing: they prepare, preserve and control the flow of information and the relationships between the other processes.

Next, all the tools of level 2 are shown. At this level, all possible configurations of a Supply Chain, as well as each of the participating links, are included and drawn. It is determined what type of plan or strategy is associated with each of the operations dependent on them, the provisioning policy of each of the members, the type of manufacturing if any, the selected distribution mode and the reverse logistics concerning the processes of return of products in case of defect, repair or excess.

Figure 7: Level 2 Process Categories.

Level 3: At this level the different processes of the Supply Chain are represented in a more detailed way by decomposing the Categories in Process Elements. They are presented in logical sequence (with rectangles and arrows) with information and materials inputs and outputs. Furthermore, the performance of each process and element is evaluated through indices, which allows to identify the different

performance levels among the processes and elements of the Supply Chain.

Level 4: This stage involves the implementation of Supply-Chain Managing Practices within the company.

3.2. Reverse logistics model based on the SCOR

To develop a reverse logistics model, it is important to have knowledge of all the benefits that this system can bring to it, in addition to the problems that may arise throughout the implementation and subsequent application.

Reverse Logistics in this project is associated with the return of products that meet their life cycle, and therefore, encompass the processes associated with recycling, reuse and re-manufacturing. The main phases identified in the previous chapter are

- **Collection:** stage referred to the recovery and transportation of the products. Collection responsibility can be supported by customers, distributors, retailers or by third parties. In the case of very expensive products, companies generally implement a repair or distribution network in order to serve the different markets and that the collection process is carried out directly³. The transport of the collected products will be carried out depending on the product and the complexity of the network, in some cases a classification of the products and components at the collection point must first be carried out while In other cases, the classification will be carried out after transport to the place where the materials will be recovered.
- **Classification:** it involves the state review of the products and components. From this stage depends the decision of the type of treatment that will be given to the products to recycle, re-manufacture or reuse. The complexity of this stage will depend on the size of the business network.
- **Treatment or Processing:** it is composed of 3 main processes according to the state in which the products are found: recycling, reuse and re-manufacturing, which are defined below.
- **Redistribution:** it is the final process of reverse logistics in which products are ready for their new life cycle.

³ (Aït-Kadj et al., 2012)

In this case, the SCOR model processes required for a Reverse Logistics system are described within the *Make* and *Return* phases because the first one deals with recycling, remanufacturing, reuse and the second with reverse flow of products.

Once identified the two main processes at first level, the key processes addressed at level 2 for each one will be:

- Make to stock vs. Make to order vs. Engineer to order for Source
- MRO (maintenance, Repair and operations)

Starting with *MAKE* process, as mentioned, it describes the activities related to the transformation of materials into products or the creation of services, i.e., assembly, chemical processes, maintenance, repair, review, recycling, restoration, remanufacturing and other activities involved in the transformation of materials into products.

<p>M1 Make-to-Stock</p>	<p>The manufacturing process adds value to products through mixing, separation, training, machining and chemical processes. The resulted products are intended to be shipped from finished goods or off-platform, can be completed prior to receipt of the customer's order and are generally produced with a calendar established according to the sales forecast. Customers do not put specifications or details on product orders.</p>
<p>M2 Make-to-Order</p>	<p>Scheduling of operations should be executed according to the production plans for specific parts or products in specific quantities and the planned availability of resources. The programming includes the sequence, the standard configurations and the production itself. In general, intermediate production activities are coordinated prior to the programming of the operations that must be carried out to produce a finished good.</p>

<p>M3 Engineer-to-order</p>	<p>It involves the process of developing, designing, validating and finally using a manufacturing process to develop products or services based on the requirements of a specific customer. This action requires work instructions and material routes according to customer needs</p>
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Table 4: MAKE sub -processes. Source: The supply Chain Council. 2010.

The following scheme shows all the processes (from level 1 to level 3) involved in *MAKE*:

Figure 8: MAKE processes scheme.

The two activities/processes to address in a reverse logistics chain are *Production and testing* and *Waste Disposal*, as detailed below.

<p>Production and testing</p>	<p>This process is defined as a series of activities carried out in the product to convert it from raw material to a semi-finished or finished product state with added value, in order to re-enter them in their respective supply chains.</p>
<p>Waste Disposal</p>	<p>It involves the activities associated with the collection and management of waste produced during the production and testing process</p>

Table 5: Production and Testing; Waste Disposal processes. MAKE process.

Furthermore, *RETURN* process defines the activities associated with the inverse flows of the products, i.e. return need identification, product disposition decision, return programming and shipment. Specifically, this process is divided into two types, *Source RETURN* and *Delivery RETURN* to differentiate whether the return is internal or made by users at the end of life. In this case, and considering a circular model, the process involved are shown in the table below.

DR2 Deliver Return MRO (Maintenance, Repair and Overhaul) product	The receipt of products or goods for Maintenance, Repair and Review as defined in the maintenance plans, referred to used products to be re-used
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Table 6: RETURN sub -process involved in reverse logistics related to a circular model. Source: The supply Chain Council. 2010

Likewise, the following scheme shows all the processes (from level 1 to level 3) involved in a Deliver Return Product:

Figure 9: Delivery RETURN MRO products processes scheme.

The two critical activities/processes to address in a reverse logistics chain are *MRO products receipt* and *MRO products transfer*, as detailed below

MRO product receipt	The service provider receives and verify the MRO product along with the authorisation return and other documentation and prepare the item for transfer
MRO product transfer	The service provider transfers the MRO product to the appropriate process to implement the disposition decision.

Table 7: MRO product receipt and MRO product transfer processes. Delivery RETURN MRO process.

As a result, the following figure proposes a Generic Reverse Logistics System for any type of industry taking into account the processes described by the SCOR in addition to the recycling, reuse and re-manufacturing processes described.

Figure 10: Reverse logistics scheme on SCOR model considering the MAKE and RETURN processes.

All these processes are linked to different costs which are included in the table below.

Process	Description	Cost
Product Identification	Location and quantity of products to collect	Product identification cost
Product Return	Product deliver from user to collection center or any entity in charge of this activity.	Deliver (transport) cost
Product collection/disposal (retailer, producer, etc.)	Product collection to warehousing or classification centres (can be developed by users, retailers, dealers third parties...)	Collection cost (transport cost)
Product Receipt and warehousing	Receipt and verification of the products in a designated place.	Receipt and warehousing cost
Classification and Diagnosis	Products and components conditions checking	Classification and diagnostic tests cost
Processing and Testing (recycling, re-manufacturing and reuse)	Activities needed to re-enter products to the supply chain	Production and testing cost. Energy cost
Waste Disposal	Collection and management of waste produced during the production and testing process	Waste disposal cost

Table 8: Processes description and associated costs involved in the reverse logistics chain according to the SCOR model

3.2.1 SCOR reverse logistic model for the Automotive sector

Following the previous generic model, the reverse logistics scheme based on the SCOR model for the automotive sector is shown below:

Figure 11: Automotive sector-Reverse logistics scheme on SCOR model considering the MAKE and RETURN processes.

As will be apparent, in this case, the first activity refers to “Product return” at its end of life, i.e. vehicle is left in:

- Car dealerships: user decides to change his vehicle and dealer manages it (re-selling to a different user or to a scrapyard)
- Scrapyards (Authorised Treatment Facilities): user directly disposes his vehicle to this centre.

Process	Description	Stakeholders involved	Cost
Vehicle Return (car dealers, scrapyards)	Vehicles disposal at their end of life, directly to scrapyards or through car dealers	User, Car dealers, Scrapyards (Authorised Treatment Facilities)	Vehicle return cost
Vehicle dismantling / Product Identification (plastics, foams, metals...) / Recovering	In case of ending up on a scrapyard (ATF), this activity first addresses the decontamination of end-of-life vehicles (batteries, liquids...). After that, an estimation of products location and	Scrapyards (Authorised Treatment Facilities)	Decontamination cost Dismantling cost

	quantity than can be recovered (plastics, foams, metals...) is carried out.		
Product collection/disposal	Product collection to warehousing or classification centres. Disposal of contaminants elements (specialised companies)	Scrapyards (ATF), Treatment centres, Waste management companies	Collection cost (transport cost)
Classification and Diagnosis	Products and components conditions checking.	Treatment centres	Classification and diagnostic tests cost (not very high, usually related to 1 hour of specialist operator) Treatment and recovering costs
Product Receipt and warehousing	Receipt and verification of the products in a designated place.	Treatment centres	Receipt and warehousing cost
Processing and production (recycling, remanufacturing and reuse)	Activities needed to re-enter products to the supply chain. Specifically, plastics and textiles are re-entered to the manufacturing chain. <u>The result is a new vehicle manufactured with recycled material</u>	Treatment centres, Production plants	Production and testing cost. Energy cost
Waste Disposal	Collection and management of waste produced during the production process	Treatment centres, Production plants	Waste disposal cost

Table 9: Processes characterisation in reverse logistics in the automotive sector base on SCOR model.

Therefore, the figure below shows the reverse logistics operations including the stakeholders' role:

Figure 12: Automotive circular model based on SCOR model.

The design of the following value chain has been validated by the partners participating in the different demonstrator cases associated with the automotive sector: MICROCAB, MAIER, TECNARO, CRF, TUDELFT, COVENTIVE, NTT, OAKDENE HOLLINS, FCBA, BELLVER, AIMPLAS.

3.2.2 SCOR reverse logistic model for the Furniture sector

Likewise, the figure below shows the reverse logistics scheme based on the SCOR model for the furniture sector:

Figure 13: Furniture sector-Reverse logistics scheme on SCOR model considering the MAKE and RETURN processes.

In this case, the “return” activity refers the step to reintegrate the furniture piece (or some of its parts) into the production chain, at the end-of-life. In this context, those pieces are recovered by:

- Collection points (clean points): directly users or by a collection service, end-of-life furniture are channelled to collection points in the area. Specifically, local legislation does not allow to dispose this type of goods on the street (close to waste bins) in most of EU countries. Therefore, local authorities make available a free collection service
- Retailers: recently, several retailers have undertaken initiatives for recovering end-of-life furniture, by encouraging consumers to bring such furniture to their premises in exchange for cash or discount vouchers for use in their business. In this way, they can treat/recover such products and sell them again, while providing a sustainable business image. At the same time, small second-hand shops have also proliferated
- Second-hand markets: in many cities, markets are regularly held on municipal land where users sell second-hand furniture

Process	Description	Stakeholders involved	Cost
Furniture Return (public collection service, retailers)	Furniture collected by local service at their end of life, or deposited/re-sold to retailers	User, Local Administration, retailers	Service cost (Local Administration), repurchase incentive/cost
Product Identification (piece, parts...)	This activity involves the first product quality estimation and parts that can be recovered; in addition, it addresses the landfill separation	Retailers, Waste Managers	Identification cost
Product collection/disposal (from collection points)	Retailers often have their own treatment/processing facilities. This activity refers the transport from collection points to those facilities	Retailers	Collection cost (transport cost)

Product Receipt and warehousing	Receipt verification of products in a treatment plant and the products in a	Retailers	Receipt and warehousing cost
Classification and Diagnosis	Products and components conditions checking (in a deeper way)	Retailers /Treatment centres	Classification and diagnostic tests cost
Processing and Testing (repairing, recycling, remanufacturing and reuse)	Activities needed to restore or re-enter products to the supply chain	Treatment centres, Production plants	Repairing cost Production and testing cost Energy cost
Waste Disposal	Collection and management of waste produced during the production and testing process	Production plants	Waste disposal cost

Table 10: Processes characterisation in reverse logistics in the furniture sector base on SCOR model.

As in the previous case, the design of this value chain has been validated by the main partners participating in the different demonstrator cases associated with the furniture sector: MORETTI, AKZONOBEL, KEAS, NTT, IRIS, OAKDENE HOLLINS, COVENTRY U., WARWICK U., NTT, LIPOR, CNR, TOMRA, CONENOR.

Therefore, the figure below shows the reverse logistics operations including the stakeholders' role:

Figure 14: Furniture circular model based on SCOR model.

3.2.3 SCOR reverse logistic model for the Construction sector

Finally, similarly to the previous sector, next figure shows the reverse logistics scheme based on the SCOR model for the construction (outdoor furniture) sector:

Figure 15: Construction sector-Reverse logistics scheme on SCOR model considering the MAKE and RETURN processes.

This case is very similar to the furniture sector, the “return” activity refers the step to reintegrate the pieces (or some of its parts) into the production chain, at the end-of-life. In this context, those pieces are recovered by:

- Collection points (clean points): by municipal collection service, outdoor furniture pieces are channelled to collection points in the area. Specifically, local legislation does not allow to dispose this type of goods on the street (close to waste bins) in most of EU countries. Therefore, local authorities make available a free collection service. It should be noted that, in the case of parts coming from dismantling and/or demolition works, a waste management system is mandatory
- Retailers/manufacturers: at times, retailers/manufacturers have undertaken initiatives for recovering end-of-life outdoor furniture, by buying them to their owners. In this way, they can treat/recover such products or use some parts for manufacturing new ones

Process	Description	Stakeholders involved	Cost
Furniture Return (public collection service, retailers)	Pieces collected by local service at their end of life, or deposited/re-sold to retailers	User/owner, Local Administration, Waste Managers, Retailers/Manufacturers	Service cost, Repurchase cost
Product Identification (piece, parts...)	This activity involves the first product quality estimation and parts that can be recovered; in addition, it addresses the landfill separation	Retailers/Manufacturers, Waste Managers	Identification cost
Product collection/disposal (from collection points)	Retailers/Producers often have their own treatment/processing facilities. This activity refers to the transport from collection points to those facilities	Retailers/Manufacturers	Collection cost (transport cost)
Product Receipt and warehousing	Receipt and verification of the products in a treatment plant	Retailers/Producers	Receipt and warehousing cost
Classification and Diagnosis	Products and components conditions checking (in a deeper way)	Retailers/Treatment centres	Classification and diagnostic tests cost
Processing and Testing (recycling, remanufacturing and reuse)	Activities needed to restore or re-enter products to the supply chain	Treatment centres, Production plants	Production and testing cost. Energy cost
Waste Disposal	Collection and management of waste produced during the production and testing process	Production plants	Waste disposal cost

Table 11: Processes characterisation in reverse logistics in the construction sector based on SCOR model.

Likewise, the design of this value chain has been validated by the main partners participating in the different demonstrator cases

associated with the furniture sector: CONENOR, TUDELFT, NTT, IRIS, CNR, OAKDENE HOLLINS, UPC, LIPOR, AIMPLAS

Therefore, the figure below shows the reverse logistics operations including the stakeholders' role:

Figure 16: Construction (outdoor furniture) circular model based on SCOR model.

3.3. Application to Ecobulk products and KPIs definition

After describing the SCOR model, the next step is to implement it in the three different reverse supply chain involved in the ECOBULK project: automotive, furniture and building sectors.

It follows from previous sections that reverse logistics may have a narrow or broad scope:

- The narrow scope refers to the actual movement and management of reverse flows of products/parts/materials from customers to suppliers. The focus then is on logistics issues such as transportation modes and routing, pick-up scheduling, and the use of third-party logistics providers to optimize the logistics capability (Kumar and Dao, 2006)
- The broader scope includes activities that support the management of used products including picking them up, sorting them out, and reusing them in different ways (Dowlatshahi, 2000)

First, as a result of the section 2, after analysing the processes involved in the reverse logistics chain, the three major activities of reverse logistics are: **collection, inspection and sorting, and product recovery.**

As previously mentioned, with the aim of optimise the operation, i.e, minimising enforcement costs, easing and boosting processes development and obtaining valuable products, in a healthy, safe and sustainable environment for each of these activities have been identified a list of parameters with an outstanding importance and relevance for their design and development. For this purpose, the different tasks that make up these activities have been taken considered

1. **Collection:** it refers to all activities rendering used products availability and moving them physically to some point where further treatment is conducted for product recovery (Sasikumar and Kannan, 2008).

Related to this activity, two decision criteria are identified: location-allocation of collection centres and methods of collection.

- Location-allocation of collection centres: several multi-stage, multi-product and multi-level mixed-integer models (MILP) have been developed in the last two decades to optimise the distribution on this type of nodes with the aim of increasing the collection activity.

Specifically, the **key performance indicators (KPIs)** identified for this issue are the following:

- Collection cost
- Processing cost
- Value added recovery
- Energy use
- Waste generation
- Level of social acceptability
- User (end-of-life) accessibility (close to home)

The following table shows the relation between the indicated KPIs and the factors identified in Section 2:

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Collection Cost	v	v		v	v
Processing Cost	v	v			
Value added recovery			v		
Energy Use	v				v
Waste Generation	v		v		
Level of social acceptability		v	v	v	v
User (end-of life) accessibility		v			v

Table 12: KPIs and factors related to location-allocation of collection centres (collection).

- **Methods of collection:** three different methods of collection are identified: collection by original equipment manufacturer (OEM), collection with retailers and collection with third party logistics providers.

Barker and Zabinsky (2008, 2011) in their conceptual framework for decision making in reverse logistic network design identified two collection types: proprietary collection and industry-wide collection. The first one is particularly beneficial when the company has a strong direct relationship with its customer such as a lease return relationship, or when there is high customer trade-in behaviour. In any case, collection methods depend on the type of industry and size of collection in addition to the criteria of initial investment, value added recovery, return volume, operating cost, degree of supply chain control, and level of customer satisfaction.

In this case, the study of activities involved in the collection phase resulted in the identification of the following **indicators:**

- Initial investment
- Return volume
- Operating cost (including the transport mode)
- Supply chain control
- Environmental impact
- Health and safety issues

The following table shows the relation between these KPIs and the factors identified in Section 2:

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Initial investment	✓				
Return Volume			✓		
Operating cost	✓				
Supply chain cost	✓	✓			✓
Environmental impact	✓				✓
Health and safety issues		✓		✓	

Table 13: KPIs and factors related to methods of collection (collection).

2. **Inspection and sorting:** this activity involves the operations that determine whether a given product is reusable or not, and if yes, then to what extent.

In this case, the main issues to be considered refers to: level of centralisation and degree of disassembly:

- Level of centralisation: sorting/testing can either be done at centralised location or decentralised location and discussed the trade-offs considerations. The first option is more suitable for high-cost testing procedures as it minimises the cost of testing equipments and specialised labor. However, the main drawback of this system is that the waste will be identified after its transportation to the testing facility, and therefore it implies a higher cost. The second option is often used if low cost testing procedures are available, such as for paper recycling machine refurbishing or reusable containers and equipment. In this system scrap is identified early and shipped to waste disposal center, thus reduces the transportation costs. However, testing procedures must be consistent and reliable at all centers. The network may be more complicated because scrap and usable return product are shipped in separate streams.

Finally, it should be indicated that inspection/separation may encompass disassembly, shredding, testing, sorting, and storage steps.

The main **indicators** to be considered in this phase are the following:

- Testing cost
- Product reliability requirement
- Availability of skilled labour
- Location of waste disposal sites
- Labour cost
- Volume of collection
- Waste handling, storage and transportation cost

The following table shows the relation between the mentioned KPIs and the factors identified in Section 2:

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Testing cost	✓	✓		✓	
Product reliability requirement			✓		
Availability of skilled labour	✓		✓	✓	
Location of waste disposal sites	✓	✓		✓	✓
Labour cost	✓		✓		
Volume of collection		✓	✓	✓	✓
Waste handling, storage and transportation cost	✓	✓		✓	✓

Table 14: KPIs and factors related to level of centralisation (inspection and sorting).

- Degree of disassembly: it comprises a systematic method of separating a product into its constituent parts, components, subassemblies or other groupings and it is also used to remove the toxic elements.

The most common **indicators** considered with the aim of defining this activity and increasing its efficiency are the following:

- Value recovery
- Disassembly cost
- Processing cost
- Landfill cost
- Incineration cost
- Environmental impact of processing
- Environmental impact of landfill
- Environmental impact of incineration

The following table shows the relation between these KPIs and the factors identified in Section 2:

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Value recovery	✓		✓		
Disassembly cost	✓				
Processing cost	✓	✓		✓	
Landfill cost	✓			✓	✓
Incineration cost	✓			✓	✓
Environmental impact of procesing				✓	✓
Environmental impact of landfill				✓	✓
Environmental impact of incineration				✓	✓

Table 15: KPIs and factors related to degree of disassembly (inspection and sorting).

3. **Product recovery:** this activity has the objective of managing the flow of products or parts destined for remanufacturing, repairing, or disposal and to effectively use the resources. In addition, it is carried out to recover hidden economical value, to meet market requirements or to meet Government regulations. This activity involves a process including these tasks: repair, reuse, refurbish, remanufacture, cannibalize, recycle or disposal. The aim of this process is to bring the product into 'as new', starting a new cycle of use.

Sometimes this process is not economically viable for the industry. By contrast, it is an environmentally sound way to achieve many of the goals of sustainable development.

In this context, new products are reassembled from the old and, where necessary, and can produce a fully equivalent and sometimes superior-in performance and expected lifetime to the original new product.

The **indicators** to be considered in order to assess the efficiency of this activity are:

- Operating cost
- Environmental impact
- Market demand
- Technical feasibility
- Green image
- Value recovery
- Health and safety issues
- Employment generation opportunities
- Law and regulation

The following table shows the relation between above KPIs and the factors identified in Section 2:

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Operating cost	✓				
Environmental impact	✓				✓
Market demand	✓	✓			
Technical feasibility	✓	✓		✓	
Green image			✓		✓
Value recovery			✓		✓
Health and safety issues				✓	✓
Employment generation opportunities			✓		✓
Law and regulation	✓			✓	✓

Table 16: KPIs and factors related to product recovery.

Specifically, some **additional indicators** have been identified in the three analysed sectors that have to be considered.

Automotive sector

Related to this sector, and from the point of view of main stakeholders involved in this chain, those indicators are important:

- **Collection:**
 - Traceability, in order to give greater transparency to the whole chain

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Traceability	✓		✓	✓	✓

Table 17: Additional KPI and factors related to collection in automotive sector.

- **Inspection and sorting**
 - Easy identification and separation of different parts

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Easy identification and separation of different parts	✓		✓	✓	✓

Table 18: Additional KPI and factors related to inspection and sorting in automotive sector.

- **Product recovery**
 - User behavior change, to increase awareness of circular economy

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
User behavior change	✓	✓	✓		✓

Table 19: Additional KPI and factors related to product recovery in automotive sector.

Furniture sector

Similarly, in the case of furniture sector, those parameters are also considered:

- **Product recovery**
 - User behavior change, to increase awareness of circular economy (e.g. through economic incentives)
 - Establishment of quality labels/certifications, in order to enhance product liability and boost customer confidence

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
User behavior change	v		v	v	v
Establishment of quality labels/certifications			v		

Table 20: Additional KPI and factors related to product recovery in furniture sector.

Construction sector

Finally, after analysing this sector, there are some specific indicators to take into account:

- **Collection:**
 - Traceability, in order to give greater transparency to the whole chain (e.g. by using a Building Information Modelling (BIM), an innovative digital tool that communicates information relating to all phases of an asset's lifecycle and allows multiple stakeholders to collaborate more efficiently on the design, construction and operation of buildings)

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Traceability	✓		✓	✓	✓

Table 21: Additional KPI and factors related to collection in building sector.

- **Product recovery**

- User behavior change, to increase awareness of circular economy (e.g. through economic incentives)

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
User behavior change	✓	✓	✓		✓

Table 22: Additional KPI and factors related to product recovery in building sector.

After the previous analysis, the next step is to identify/establish those parameters that have **the most incidence in the transport phase**, and therefore should be taken into account in the traceability system to be developed in task 6.2 (WP6).

To this end, and based on the five groups of variables that have been defined (enforcement costs, ease of process development, obtaining value products, health and safety requirements and sustainability), the following can be assumed:

- Enforcement cost: it involves the costs related to whole transport process, i.e. vehicles/devices, facilities, staff and route
- Ease of processes development: in general, the greater or lesser ease of the processes has a direct influence on the development costs of the operation, and therefore on its

feasibility. Therefore, this variable is usually translated into an economic component (costs)

- Obtention of valuable products: it is associated with the quality of the products handled in the reverse value chain, and therefore, with the benefit that can be obtained from it (re-introduction into the production process). This variable is addressed in the WP6 Quality Assessment System
- Health and safety requirements: throughout the process associated with reverse logistics, safety and health for all agents involved (from collector to end user) must be ensured. To this end, the relevant legislation must be complied
- Sustainability: by definition, a circular model is more sustainable than a traditional linear one. Specifically, in the transport phase, it should be interesting to estimate the associated pollutant emissions

Therefore, these considerations can be summarised in the following table:

Key Indicators	Variables				
	Enforcement Cost	Ease of processes development	Obtention of Valuable products	Health and Safety requirements	Sustainability
Transport cost	✓				
Transport emissions					✓

Table 23: Most relevant KPIs and factors in the transport phase.

Specifically, for the activities being developed in the ECOBULK project, this type of indicators has been considered in the different prototypes proposed (WP4) in the three sectors.

Automotive sector

Prototypes: modular dashboard (MICROCAB); multi-layers components (MAIER); semi-structural components (CRF)

Modular dashboard

Elements: Central Console Cowlings, Dashboard highlight panel and Vehicle Cabin Sound Insulation Panels.

Figure 17: ECOBULK modular dashboard components value chain. Automotive sector.

Multi-layer components

Elements: Fascia Central Control and assembly tool.

Figure 18: ECOBULK multi-layers components value chain. Automotive sector.

It has been noted that this prototype is only used to simulate a recovered product and to help demonstrating the shredding and recyclability capabilities of ECOBULK materials.

Semi-structural components

Elements: Safety Belt Bracket and Trim Central panel.

Figure 19: ECOBULK semi-structural components value chain. Automotive sector.

Furthermore, should be noted that material recovery is not considered in the pilot case to be developed since the materials are the same that the ones used in MAIER (sample production using recovered material can be done with MAIER recovered scraps)

Furniture sector

Prototypes: modular furniture (MORETTI); Non-woven materials in sofa (FCBA)

Modular furniture

Elements: Student accommodation and meeting room in Coventry University (UK); Meeting room in Warwick University (UK); Meeting room in LIPOR (Portugal); Meeting room in FCBA (France); and Student accommodation in Camerino (Italy)

Figure 20: ECOBULK modular furniture value chain. Furniture sector.

Non-woven material in sofa

Elements: Non-woven material included in a sofa in FCBA installations (France)

Figure 21: ECOBULK non-woven material in sofa value chain. Furniture sector.

Construction sector

Prototypes: Glass-Fiber Reinforced Plastic (GFRP)-waste containing structural outdoor furniture used to develop the following elements (CONENOR, WARWICK UNIVERSITY, LIPORT AND FCBA):

- Modular shelters (UK, Finland)
- Tree Bench (Portugal)
- Drinking Fountain (Portugal)
- Recycle Bin Shelter (Portugal)
- Benches (Portugal, France, Finland)
- Tables (France)
- Wall Module (France)
- Info Cabin (Finland)

Structural outdoor furniture (universities)

Elements: Modular shelters in Coventry, Warwick and Cranfield Universities (UK)

Figure 22: ECOBULK GFRP-waste containing structural outdoor furniture in universities. Building sector.

Structural outdoor furniture (parks)

Elements: Tree Bench, Drinking Fountain and Recycled Bin Shelter (Portugal)

Figure 23: ECOBULK GFRP-waste containing structural outdoor furniture in parks. Building sector.

Structural outdoor furniture (business park)

Elements: Bench, Table and Wall Module (France)

Figure 24: ECOBULK GFRP-waste containing structural outdoor furniture in business parl. Building sector.

Structural outdoor furniture (business and open areas)

Elements: Bench, Modular Bench and Info Cabin (Finland)

Figure 25: ECOBULK GFRP-waste containing structural outdoor furniture in business and open areas. Building sector.

4. Strategies and technologies for transport and logistics optimisation

Consumers have grown increasingly comfortable with recycling. Companies can use an incentive to get users to return end-of-use and end-of-life products by exchanging empty containers for new products. The benefits of an efficient return strategy are about more than saving the planet and reducing costs.

In this respect, reverse logistics involves the collection of goods, transportation to a given location and sorting prior to remanufacturing, refurbishing, reusing or recycling or failing that, disposal. It plays an important role in the process of companies aiming to transition to a circular economy. Before setting up reverse flows, companies need to evaluate the supply chain within which the business operates. Companies may face hurdles such as complying with policies regulating the transport of waste as well as the unevenness of quality and quantity in return loads. There are cost challenges due to:

- Wide geographic dispersion of end-life product/waste distribution
- Unclear definition of collection and transport processes
- Inefficiencies due to lack of scale
- Sorting is labour intensive and requires space

In the same vein, unlike forward one, reverse logistics generates uncertainty in the system derived from the following aspects; quantity of the product that can be recovered (quantitative uncertainty); quality of the product (qualitative uncertainty); and, finally, timing where the collection of the product will take place (time uncertainty). The main factors causing this uncertainty include: end users characteristics, place of use of the product, and product's life cycle length. This uncertainty in the return flows determines to a great extent the effectiveness of the reverse logistics network, so that the phase with which the return process begins, that is, **the collection process**, is seen as a fundamental element in the design of reverse logistics networks.

In this context, cities are becoming critical areas for the collection of waste, materials and products, because of their increasing concentration of population. Therefore, they largely determine the success of reverse logistics systems. Nevertheless, the different typologies of the cities, their radial structure, the high concentration of commercial, leisure and catering areas in the city centres, as well as the different objectives of the main interest groups (manufacturers,

residents, traders, customers, local authorities, etc.), greatly condition the effectiveness of reverse logistics activities.

Currently, in general, the local authorities and other public institutions are legally responsible for the management of municipal waste and therefore plan the collection and transport of such waste in a way that contributes to the city's sustainability. However, the current trend is for these institutions to meet this responsibility by outsourcing waste management to private companies. In this way, the recovery and management of end-of-life products (reuse, remanufacturing) and products at the end of their useful life (recycling) are usually entrusted to the so-called Integrated Management Systems (IMS), (e.g. in the case of the automotive sector they are the Authorised Treatment Facilities), often non-profit organisations, promoted by manufacturers, importers and distributors, which in this way face up to their extended responsibility

Therefore, bearing in mind the latter considerations, flexibility is a fundamental aspect in order to be able to deal with the uncertainties intrinsic to reverse logistics. In this sense, and with reference to the collection and transport phase, and more specifically to the possible modes to be used, the following analysis can be addressed:

- Road mode: this is undoubtedly the mode with the greatest flexibility (volumes and distance), but also the most expensive
- Railway mode: it is an optimal mode for medium-high load volumes and longer distances, at a lower cost than road, but it requires specific infrastructure, and the journey time is longer
- Maritime mode: this is undoubtedly the most economical and sustainable mode, but it requires large volumes of cargo, port infrastructure close to the origin and destination, additional modes (multimodality), and the journey time is much longer

After this analysis, and considering the importance of flexibility in reverse logistics, and its lesser development/deployment compared to direct logistics, it seems logical to think that the most suitable mode for the design of prototype circular models is associated with **road transport**.

Moreover, there are: other important aspects for a successful circular design from the economic point of view:

- Standard components, with the aim of maximising return volumes to create optimised reverse pathways for products from the durable goods sector;
- Products designed to last;

- Design for an easy classification at the end of the useful life;
- Design criteria for manufacturing that take into account the possible useful applications of derivatives and waste
- Use of pure materials in the production processes to simplify their classification and sorting at the end of the useful life
-

Ultimately, circular economic business models should also be taken into account at design stage. Therefore, feedback mechanisms should be developed between the activities of design and the end of life.

Thereunder, the first part of this paragraph shows some success stories for circular model approach in the project study sectors are shown. Likewise, some others related to other sectors are also included.

4.1. Successful cases in the reverse logistics value chain

This paragraph addresses the identification and analysis of several best practices implemented in the three sectors analysed related to a successful circular model, in order to optimise the logistics chain.

4.1.1 Automotive sector

With 60% of the global supply going into car manufacturing, the automotive industry is the top consumer of lead in the world and according to some studies, these reserves will run out in 2030. Besides the shortages and supply challenges of the metals, rare or not, the rise in global demand for raw materials has created extraordinary price increases. For the automotive industry, these added costs are going up by several million euros year on year.

As indicative data, 12 million vehicles are taken off the roads every year in the European Union, which amounts to millions of tonnes of what actually constitutes a valuable resource⁴. The utilisation of this secondary resource, investing in recycling technologies and increasing the use of recycled material has been found to provide a promising outlook.

⁴ According to European regulations (End of Life Vehicle Directive), vehicles must be recycled to 85% from 2015.

ECOREDES. Spanish circular economy network of car dealers

Faconauto, in collaboration with *Grupo Proassa*, has developed the first Circular Economy project from the vehicle distribution network, integrating their dealers' network with authorised scrapping and workshops in a single technological environment.

The system allows telematic requesting for the following procedures to all scrapyards belonging to the *Sigrauto* network through the webpage (www.ecoredes.es):

- Withdrawal of the vehicle to proceed with its withdrawal from the Directorate-General for Traffic;
- Destruction Certificate before the environment council;
- Decontamination;
- Reuse of pieces for use in the second life market;
- Shipment to fragmenting machine.

This way, it allows to obtain the Concession, the Traffic Discharge and the Destruction Certificate, at the moment in which the Scrapping is carried out. Thus, it accelerates the management procedures with the owner of the vehicle and with public institutions in case of existing a valid *Remove Plan*.

Another advantage is the guaranteed traceability and compliance level with the waste regulations. The system shows the percentage of decontaminated waste, the total weight of the vehicle, the percentage of parts prepared for reuse, and the percentage of recovery, through the shipment to shredder.

RENAULT Closing-loop case

The circular economy was first and foremost a new economic model that Groupe Renault promoted with the Ellen MacArthur Foundation. A new way of approaching the life cycle of vehicles by extending the life of its components and materials.

In 2011, RENAULT addressed the *ICARRE95* project, (through its subsidiary Gaïa, with the aim of developing new activities in the area of material collection and recycling in collaboration with entity

specialised in the recycling of materials (SYNOVA for plastic, MTB for copper and other). Three families of materials were carefully selected at the beginning of the project. In the first phase of the project, the objectives were to increase collected volumes and to set up quality standards for recycling operations in order to avoid cross pollution. The second phase was to foster the re-use of these materials by preparing them for a new life and re-using them in the production processes. During this four-year project (2011-2015), Gaia served as an "interface" for all members of the project, allowing traceability of materials, contractual arrangements and billing. Since then, it ensures the operational feasibility of closed recycling loops developed in this project.

Objectively, one task of the ICARRE95 project was to develop solutions for better and cost-effective dismantling, and to duplicate such solutions among the dismantlers' network in collaboration with INDRA (Industry National Dismantling & Recycling Automotive). Better dismantling means well sorted and easier to valorise wastes. It means also not damaged and reused parts.

By the end of 2015, Renault group could rely on five closed loops, operated by GAIA or other affiliates by recycling the following parts: Metallic parts deriving from maintenance and services networks are sent to foundries; Copper; Polypropylene (from bumpers); Foam and textile; Platinoïd Group Metals (from used catalytic converters; and Metallic wastes from production processes.

The main figures of this initiative were:

- 30.6% of recycled materials in the total mass of new vehicles produced in Europe.
- With regards to plastic, Renault's engineers design vehicles integrating at least 7% of recycled plastic materials. This rate can go up to 17% for certain models. In the end of 2015, the mass of recycled plastic was 23.8 kg per vehicle on average. This is particularly visible in Renault Group's consumption of recycled plastic, which increased by 18.7% between 2013 and 2015.
- With regards to steel: the rate of recycled steel goes from 15% for flat steel to 100% for long steels and foundries.
- Increase in skills of different actors involved in the project.
- Better collaboration between project partners for the collection and re-use of materials.
- Setting up standards for materials dismantling and sorting to avoid cross pollution between materials

Figure 26: ICARRE95 project value chain. Challenges, limitations and solutions.

4.1.2 Furniture sector

These product group often contains significant quantities of metals, plastics and other non-renewable resources. At the same time, large amounts of energy are required to process these raw materials into refined furniture. The potential for environmental and economic savings from optimising the resource efficiency of individual products and of furniture industries as a whole is substantial.

IKEA

In 2016, IKEA presented a pilot project in Madrid (Spain) called #SalvemosLosMuebles with the aim of identifying new opportunities along the entire value chain, from raw material to new services to its customers. This strategy is reflected in the day to day of the company that results in responding to the following parts of the chain: CARE, REPAIR, CUSTOMISE, SELL, DONATE and RECYCLE

This initiative is a furniture take-back service where customers could recycle their unwanted furniture and be rewarded for being more sustainable. The take-back service enables customers to exchange their used items for IKEA vouchers. The used furniture is sold in a bid to extend the IKEA furniture lifecycle, instead of just having these items end up in landfills. Customers will be able to buy perfectly good pre-loved furniture at a fraction of the original price – and even be able to get their hands on some of IKEA’s classic pieces that are no longer in production.

In this case, as it could be verified, the user is responsible for transporting the furniture to the collection point (i.e. IKEA stores), and therefore carries out the associated costs. With the aim of being an attractive service, the user receives a reward. This way, all the stakeholders involved feel that benefit from this operation. Obviously, it should be developed in a nearby area, to not confer a too big endeavour.

Figure 27: IKEA #SalvemosLosMuebles campaign.

GISPEN circular economy

GISPEN is a Dutch producer of office furniture that has adopted circular economy strategies and practices to differentiate itself in the market and reduce its environmental impact. This circular business practices has provided GISPEN with a green image, reduced GISPEN's exposure to volatile resource prices and stimulated innovation within the company.

The circular approach of GISPEN begins with the furniture design. When designing their products, they take into account that the

materials used are renewable, the products have a long useful life, their products can be sent and transported efficiently, they can be repaired and updated easily and that it is possible to disassemble them. Thus, the pieces or the materials can be reused

This model has allowed GISPEN to reuse (resell), recondition, reuse parts and recycle its products. This is the “urban mining” concept: a new trend that is focused on extracting raw materials from the city.

The inventory of any location of all of users’ furniture is registered in an online system. The aim of this is, not only, come up with a maintenance and exchange plan but also to be transparent in the whole chain, the added value of maintenance and to ensure a closed loop system.

Related to the return value (the amount users receive when they exchange a piece of furniture), it is a percentage of the original acquisition price. It is determined at the end of a product’s use time.

Figure 28: GISPEN Circular Business Model.

Public waste collection services

In general, many municipalities in the EU have implemented a bulky waste management system (furniture, household appliances, etc.), including plants called "clean points" for their classification, disassembly and dismantling. The collection can be carried out by users or by a public free home delivery service. In many cases, this service has a daily frequency (working days) and it is possible to request it on

other occasions. Once the notice is made, the collection service schedules a date. This way, it is guaranteed that the furniture is moved to the waste treatment plants, where the components that may be useful and recyclable are extracted, and the appropriate treatment is given to them.

In most cases, this type of service is associated with the existing regulations on waste management. In this context, this regulation prohibits in many cases the deposition of large-volume waste on the street.

Figure 29: Moving “clean point” in Madrid (Spain).

This example presents a model with a public management of waste residues. Thus, the Municipality is responsible for the whole process from collection to treatment (previous to industry remanufacturing)

Specifically, in Italy, CONAI-Consortio Nazionale Imballaggi (a private non-profit organisation) is responsible for promoting selective collection, sorting, recovery and recycling of packaging waste in Italy (encompassing packaging of both fast-moving consumer goods and industrial products). For the recovery operations of individual materials, CONAI coordinates the activities of six Material Consortia. Rilegno (for wood) is one of them. In this case, a specific agreement between recyclers or guarantors and local authorities exists for packaging and non-packaging waste. The Consortium pays at 3.33 €/ton. Furthermore, there is no sorting for this material and all the collect wood is directly sent to recycling/recovery.

4.1.3 Construction sector (outdoor furniture)

In the field of construction, and specifically related to urban furniture, the main activity on circular economy is focused on the eco-design. Specialists believe that it is easier to introduce recycled components

into them. One of the novelties they bring is the use of additive manufacturing, known as 3D printing, for discontinued spare parts.

iURBAN – Contrary to planned obsolescence

It is a clear example of a company linked to the circular economy, a new productive model that can be a source of opportunities for SMEs. This model is based on the need to break with the linear scheme of "take, manufacture and throw" and create a new economic paradigm that is more environmentally friendly. To this end, it seeks to maximise resources and minimise waste generation. Therefore, it implies new market niches for companies that help optimise these processes and introduce creative solutions in areas such as recycling and energy saving.

Specifically, this Spanish start-up is working jointly with the technology company Telefonica on the transformation of traditional telephone booths into portable tourist offices, with the aim of returning a deficit business to the revenue path. At the same time, these new "cabins" include mobile charging points and interactive screens that allow making selfies. To this purpose, iURBAN has developed a software that allows a second life to this type of urban element.

Figure 30: Re-converted telephone booth in Málaga (Spain).

Plastic Wood

SOLTECO is a recycled plastic transformation company that produces plastic profiles and all types of furniture, which comes from 100% recycled and recyclable materials.

Its activity focuses on a specialised process of collecting and selecting plastic, grinding it, separating the spurious material and subjecting it to extrusion to compact the fluid. Thus, a total homogeneity in the mixture is achieved. The fine pellet is transferred to the mould extruders, which are responsible for shaping the profiles that will later become pieces of furniture. The waste treatment process with INNOVEQ technology, allows the creation of a new recycled material with great features for its application to daily life. Additionally, it has the added advantage of not needing maintenance.

In this sector, CMPLASTIK is another Spanish company with a similar activity, giving a second life by recycling waste of plastic origin that has been removed in landfills. There are many projects that this company is developing in the areas of street and street furniture, both nationally and internationally and that are already being implemented successfully in several municipalities. Specifically, in the Valencia area, two projects stand out: the furniture at the entrance to the Natural Park of *La Albufera* (as an activity of the *LIFE FUTURE project*⁵); and, the park in the town of Carlet, which includes 20% of rice straw made benches.

These benches whose aesthetics imitate wood have many advantages for the environment compared to traditional wooden benches, since they are made with 100% recycled and recyclable materials.

Likewise, this company also develops traffic and signage displays, composting elements and playgrounds units with the same technique.

⁵ LIFE FUTURE a European project that involves the development and validation of the Green Urban Furniture (GUF) Tool, which is an online device to support public bodies on the decision making related to the purchase of more environmentally friendly urban furniture. It has been co-funded with the support of the LIFE financial instrument of the European Union and the Valencian Regional Government through IVACE

Figure 31: Picnic tables made with l'Albufera rice straw and chufa cultivation plastic. CMPLASTIK.

The Zero Waste Lab

The residents of Thessaloniki, Greece, can now recycle their plastic waste into 3D printed furniture for the city, using a new laboratory set up by Rotterdam studio The New Raw.

The Zero Waste Lab is the latest enterprise of The New Raw's plastic recycling initiative, Print Your City, established in collaboration with drinks brand Coca Cola. It offers local residents a recycling facility for their plastic waste as well as the ability to choose what the waste is turned into, with a robotic 3D-printing arm that can transform the sorted plastic into street furniture.

Users can customise the furniture via a website, choosing between different colours and functionalities and also selecting which public space in the city they would like to see it in. Options for each object include a planter, a bike rack, a feeding bowl for dogs and a bookcase, among other functions. The furniture is made primarily from polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene (PE) plastics.

As a result, Hanth Park in central Thessaloniki became the first public space to be redesigned with Print Your City furniture in January 2019. To this end, more than 800 kg of plastic waste were recycled, and more than 2,900 citizens of Thessaloniki voted where and how they wanted to see the new furniture of the city.

ZERO WASTE LAB

Figure 32: Urban furniture in the Hanth Park in Thessaloniki (Greece).

4.1.4 Other sectors

Circul8 -The Circular Economy Software

Cicul8 is a cloud-based software suite for the Circular Economy and encompasses multiple regulations and waste streams as well as supporting a wide range of stakeholders in the Circular Economy. Being deployed in 20 countries, across 4 continents, managing 8 million tons of waste and €2.7B of revenue - It is built to manage every step in the process from individual producer responsibility (IPR) take-back through to the final recycling of resources that can be fed back into the manufacturing process, closing the loop. Circul8 orchestrates resources and processes – optimising the business and providing valuable insights to management.

Cicul8 provides an online, real-time portal, which is accessible to every user in the process, where they can perform multiple tasks in order for a complete management of the entire process

At the same time, this tool considers the following issues: Traceability; Accountability; Checkpoint; Evidence; Supplier Qualification

Figure 33: Circul8 WASTE prebuilt modules.

Specifically, this tool has a module that addresses the reverse logistics chain from the producer to the consolidation centre. This is Circul8 WASTE. Related to logistics activities, it allows to coordinate the activities of the different users in the collection network and supply chain. It provides a self-service solution, whereby:

- collection points issue a pick-up request
- logistics operators are notified
- logistics operators report on the execution of the operations and destination sites
- the destination sites are informed and report back on the waste received and recycled

WASTE attributes and compliance documentation are configured in the system to ensure full traceability for each activity and complete accountability of each stakeholder in the operation. Logistics partners collect and deliver the waste; treatment plants recycle the waste; and both provide compliance documentation for their operations.

The Billing module manages all supplier pricelists for easy validation of financial flows and calculation of the granular costs of each operation (per stream, territory, supplier, etc.).

Figure 34: Circul8 WASTE module.

MarketplaceHUB

The aim of this platform is to facilitate business to business reuse opportunities for secondary materials worldwide. It provides geo-referenced information on worldwide operating material marketplaces. This way, it allows to identify a wide range of available secondary raw materials by categories. Indeed, the main challenge addressed are related to providing valuable information on secondary material (supply location, quantity and frequency, price transparency, and quality)

 Marketplace
HUB

A network
of circular economy
practitioners

Figure 35: MarketplaceHUB platform.

CIRCULARISE: blockchain technology

This Dutch firm is developing a blockchain-based communication protocol called “smart questioning” to promote value chain transparency without public disclosure of datasets or supply chain partners. This tool aims to remove main barriers related to product information reliability, i.e., traceability and transparency. Data on components, supply chain and costs are often missing and there is no central platform or specific tool that allows to obtain required data. This is the CIRCULARISE *Smart Questioning* technology basis.

By drawing up *smart contracts*⁶ among different stakeholders, it is possible to do business without an intermediary by using a decentralised application.

This technology has three different interfaces to interact with the protocol: CIRDASH, to generate carriers, provide data and use Smart Questioning tool; CIRAPP, to provide information to end users and facilitate communication between consumer and manufacturer; and, CIRAPI, to create and integrate an own app.

Finally, it is possible to generate unique identifiers called CIRLABELS and attach them to materials, parts and products. To this aim QR, RFID and NFC codes or any IOT enabled device can be used.

Figure 36: CIRCULARISE concept origin.

⁶ Smart contracts are self-executing contracts with the terms of the agreement between buyer and seller being directly written into lines of code. The code and the agreements contained therein exist across a distributed, decentralized blockchain network

TagItSmart! project

This H2020 funded project aims at creating the first Internet of Things (IOT) platform based on smart tags that allows an open ecosystem of connected objects. Thus, its objective is to improve the intelligence of everyday items by means of printed labels, that allow the digital interaction with them. To this effect, this project addresses the use of FunCodes which provide information that changes according to external conditions or events that occur during its life cycle.

In this context, one of its main challenges is to create a TagItSmart! ecosystem comprising all relevant stakeholders to ensure wide take up, sustainable development, expansion and exploitation of TagItSmart! functionalities.

The technology used combines the potential of functional or intelligent inks (which change according to temperature, humidity, elapsed time, etc.), ink-printed circuits (PCBs) and digital (such as QR or Datamatrix codes) and electronic (such as NFC tags or short-range communication) markers, so that it can identify any product in the cloud and provide new features impossible to achieve in an analogue way.

In short, it is intended to create the perfect bridge between suppliers, consumers and their objects.

Figure 37: TagItSmart project general objectives framework.

PlastiCircle project

PlastiCircle is a H2020 programme project with the aim of promoting the transition towards a circular economy, and to contribute to the European Union's waste management and recycling targets to 2030.

Specifically, it addresses the whole reverse chain - from collection to transport, sorting to recycling -in order to transform waste into valuable products. The main objective is reinventing the plastic packaging treatment process to obtain higher recycling rates, better quality and cheaper secondary raw materials, as well as better recovery and valorisation within the same value chain.

One of the scopes is the improvement of transport routes, i. e. showing the different approaches in which route optimization can be solved, identifying the different advantages of each method and giving an historical perspective in which vehicle route problems (VRP) had evolution.

In this context, a machine learning algorithm is developed. It is based on a predictive model which allows to choose what containers should be collected in a concrete time considering its filling level. The specific objective is to minimise the cost by means of the energy consumption, time or the different constraints a waste management company may have.

Finally, a general and basic methodology for the environmental impact assessment of the routes developed is defined, taking into account different environmental KPIs related to the transport phase.

The presented methodology needs to be adapted for the specific case of each city, considering their characteristics and necessities, and taking into consideration the limitation of resources in some cases.

Figure 38: Routing problem graph - Container selection-Phase I. PLASTICIRCLE project.

4.1.5 Best practices and technologies review

As a result of the analysis of different best practices and successful cases, it has been found that information sharing, transparency and collaboration are widely recognised as essential catalysts for a circular economy. To use one company's 'waste' as 'food' for another, stakeholders need to access the right information at the right time. Often, however, information sharing risks a stakeholder's competitive advantage.

In this sense, knowing the life course of articles, from their end of life to their reuse and remanufacturing (including collection, treatment and reintegration into the production chain), is critical for the designing and creating circular economies. Likewise, in addition to its journey, it is also essential to have relevant information throughout the entire process, such as the associated cost data, participating agents and their responsibilities, as well as an estimate of the benefits to be obtained at the end of the process (business model)

In this context, an accurate costs analysis and a clear economic benefit are critical factors in order to define and foster circular business models.

Specifically, waste collection and transport operations account for 60-80% of overall costs and are therefore of great economic importance.

At this stage it is of vital importance to determine the collection routes, collection frequency, transport conditions and to determine the most economical alternative(s) taking into account the costs associated to such management

For this reason, it is necessary to have a tool to assess and evaluate the different alternatives available for the design and establishment of specific circular business models for the project study sectors. This tool will take into account the different criteria identified in section 3.2 of this document, and which refer to technical, economic, environmental and social aspects.

5. Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) tool

Multicriteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) is a set of methods that, explicitly and systematically, facilitates to consider different criteria for decision making. It allows developing a decision-making process with a more global perspective, making explicit the values or dimensions and their relative importance in this process.

Specifically, the tool to develop should implements the AHP (Analytic Hierarchy Process) to evaluate the main parameters involved the feasibility of implementing a waste/end-life product recovery plan.

The main objective of this tool is to assess different scenarios with end-life products from the three sectors that reach the minimum values established for considered criteria: economic, technical, environmental, social and legal.

- Economic: it assesses the costs associated with the different activities of the logistics chain based on parameters such as: collection process, vehicle typologies, covered distance, benefit obtained. Likewise, payment to users for deposit of the product will be taken into account, if applicable.
- Technical: it assesses the technical requirements that are needed for the development and implementation of the inverse logistics chain raised (minimum volumes, traceability, monitoring, etc.) associated with the defined business model.
- Environmental: impact estimation for each alternative associated with the scenarios proposed (e.g. CO₂ emission calculation for the different transport options)
- Social: in this case, it is considered the existence of aspects that enhance citizen participation in developing business models that boost the circular economy (e.g. incentives, agreements with consumer associations, etc.)
- Legal: it assesses the existing regulatory requirements

The next figure shows the five criteria scheme:

Figure 39: Multi-Criteria Analysis scheme.

The methodology used to design this MCDA tool is CRITIC. This method, originally by Diakoulaki, Mavrotas and Papayannakis, was presented in 1995 in the journal Computers Operation Research (vol. 22, no. 7, pp. 763-777). Its name is the acronym of CRiteria Importance Through Intercriteria Correlation, and it weights each criterion according to the expression, starting from the data that the different alternatives take for this criterion.

$$w_{j..} = s_{j..} * \sum (1 - r_{jk})$$

Being:

- w_j = weight of criterion j
- s_j = standard deviation of criterion j
- r_{jk} = Correlation coefficient between criteria j and k

With CRITIC the weight of a criterion is greater the greater is its variance (greater standard deviation), and the greater different information from the other contributing criteria (lower correlation coefficient between columns)

For its application and in order to be able to compare magnitudes, a normalisation is carried out prior to their range by transforming them to values between 0 and 1

The standard deviation of each criterion is obtained by applying the known formula:

$$s_j = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (x_j - x^-)^2}{n - 1}}$$

where:

- x_j = criterion value j
- x^- = standard deviation of criterion j
- r_{jk} = Correlation coefficient between criteria j and k

Likewise, using the formula of Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, the different correlation coefficients between the criteria can be calculated

$$r_{jk} = \frac{cov(j, k)}{s_j * s_k}$$

where:

- $cov(j, k) = \sum_{i=1}^n (j_i - j^-) * (k_i - k^-)$

The objective of this activity is to align as much as possible the functionalities of the MCDT tool with the technology to be implemented in the platform, and more specifically to the transport and logistics system. For this reason, and in order to adjust as much as possible to the pilot activities to be carried out, it is necessary to adapt these functionalities (criteria parameters, and their weights) to the business models to be developed by the industrial partners.

In this context the following aspects are considered:

- In the economic field, the first parameter that can be estimated is the cost associated along the whole process. Specifically, as far as logistics activities are concerned, the cost associated with transport in each of the phases will be estimated (included in the integrated logistics module of the platform - WP6)
- In the technical field, the mentioned traceability system (developed in WP6) will raise the different options of the following destination, depending on the volumes of product, its quality, and the different destination alternatives (depending on the location of collection, treatment, and manufacturing centres)
- In the environmental field, emissions in each transport stage will be estimated (in the traceability module)
- As far as legal aspects are concerned, it is understandable that all business models to be proposed and implemented must comply with the regulations and legislation in force at all levels (European, national, regional and local)

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